

NOTES

3. J. D HUNT and K. A. JACKSON, *Trans. AIME*, 1966, 236, 843.
4. P. S. BASSI, N. K. SHARMA and M. K. SHARMA, *Cryst. Res. Technol.*, 1983, 18, 1191.
5. P. S. BASSI, N. K. SHARMA and M. K. SHARMA, *Indian J. Technol.*, in the press.
6. "International Critical Tables", ed. E. W. WASHBURN, McGraw-Hill, New York, 1927, Vol. IV.
7. B. L. SHARMA, N. K. SHARMA and P. S. BASSI, *Cryst. Res. Technol.*, 1982, 17, 9, 1117.
8. M. K. SHARMA, Ph.D. Thesis, University of Jammu, 1983.

studies prompted us to synthesise some new compounds (1) as possible antineoplastic agents in which the pyrazole moiety is linked at one side of azo linkage and benzothiazole to the other side, so as to increase the overall activity of the azo group.

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Synthesis of some New Benzothiazolylazopyrazoles

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BIOLOGICAL importance of azo compounds is well known for their use as antineoplastics¹, antidiabetics², antiseptics^{3,4} and other useful chemotherapeutics⁵, e.g. *N,N*-bis (2-chlorophenyl)-*p*-phenylazoaniline has been found to possess tumor inhibitory activity⁶. Moreover, pyrazoles and benzothiazoles are also considered as potent biologically active compounds⁷⁻¹⁴. It has been found that the activity of azo linkage increases on the incorporation of suitable heterocyclic nuclei. These

The compounds reported herein have been synthesised by reacting various 2-benzothiazolylhydrazono-1-(*N*-aminophenyl)-1,3-butanedione, 3-benzothiazolylhydrazonopentane-2,4-dione, 2-benzothiazolylhydrazono-1-[*N*-amino(2-chlorophenyl)]-butane-1,3-dione with thiosemicarbazide. The structure of these compounds have been established on the basis of elemental analysis, and ir, nmr and mass spectral studies.

Experimental

Ir spectra (KBr) were scanned on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer, uv-vis spectra on a Carl-Zeiss specord spectrophotometer, umr spectra (CDCl₃ + TFA) using TMS as internal standard on a Perkin-Elmer R-35 instrument, and mass spectra

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA AND CHARACTERISTICS OF SOME SUBSTITUTED-4-BENZOTHAZOLYL-AZO-*N*-THIOCARBAMOYL PYRAZOLES (1)*

Sl. no.	R	R ₁	R ₂	M.p	Yield %	Colour	Mol. formula
1.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	238	50	Orange	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₆ S ₂
2.	4-CH ₃	CH ₃	CH ₃	176	55	Yellow	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₆ S ₂
3.	5-CH ₃	CH ₃	CH ₃	242	55	Orange	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₆ S ₂
4.	6-CH ₃	CH ₃	CH ₃	250	50	Yellow	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₆ S ₂
5.	6-Cl	CH ₃	CH ₃	264	45	Orange	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₆ S ₂ Cl
6.	6-Br	CH ₃	CH ₃	250	50	Orange	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₆ S ₂ Br
7.	6-NO ₂	CH ₃	CH ₃	166	60	Orange	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₇ O ₂ S ₂
8.	4-OCH ₃	CH ₃	CH ₃	110	50	Orange	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂
9.	5-OCH ₃	CH ₃	CH ₃	226	55	Red	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂
10.	6-OC ₂ H ₅	CH ₃	CH ₃	120	45	Yellow	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂
11.	H	CH ₃	NHC ₆ H ₅	220	55	Orange	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₇ S ₂
12.	4-CH ₃	CH ₃	NHC ₆ H ₅	150	60	Red	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₇ S ₂
13.	5-CH ₃	CH ₃	NHC ₆ H ₅	210	60	Red	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₇ S ₂
14.	6-CH ₃	CH ₃	NHC ₆ H ₅	230	55	Yellow	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₇ S ₂
15.	6-Cl	CH ₃	NHC ₆ H ₅	194	50	Yellow	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₇ S ₂ Cl
16.	6-Br	CH ₃	NHC ₆ H ₅	184	55	Yellow	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₇ S ₂ Br
17.	6-NO ₂	CH ₃	NHC ₆ H ₅	200	60	Yellow	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₈ O ₂ S ₂
18.	4-OCH ₃	CH ₃	NHC ₆ H ₅	190	45	Red	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₇ O ₂ S ₂
19.	5-OCH ₃	CH ₃	NHC ₆ H ₅	130	50	Red	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₇ O ₂ S ₂
20.	6-OC ₂ H ₅	CH ₃	NHC ₆ H ₅	250	45	Red	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₇ O ₂ S ₂
21.	5-NO ₂ -6-CH ₃	CH ₃	NHC ₆ H ₅	161	60	Orange	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₈ O ₂ S ₂
22.	H	CH ₃	NHC ₆ H ₄ Cl	166	50	Orange	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₇ O ₂ Cl
23.	H	C=O	C=O	236	40	Orange	C ₁₁ H ₈ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂

*All compounds gave consistent N and S analysis.

(70 eV) on a JEOL JMS-DX 300 spectrometer. All melting points are uncorrected.

4-Benzothiazolylazo-N-thiocarbamoyl-3-methyl-5-aminophenylpyrazole: Appropriate derivative of 2-benzothiazolylhydrazonobutyl-1-aminophenyl-1,3-dione^{1*} (0.005 mol) was refluxed with thiosemicarbazide (0.005 mol) in alcohol and acetic acid mixture for 6 h. The product obtained after cooling was filtered and repeatedly recrystallised from DMF and water mixture, m.p. 250° (Found: N 22.12, S, 14.22. C₂₀H₁₉N₇OS₂ calcd. for: N, 22.47, S, 14.64%); λ_{max} (MeOH) 400 nm (-N=N-); M^+ at m/e 437; ν_{max} (KBr) 1590 (N=N), 1610 (C=C or C=N), 1170 (C=S), 3420 (NH) and 750–800 cm⁻¹ (substituted phenyl). The nmr spectra (CDCl₃ + TFA) of compd. sl. no 20 (Table 1) displayed signals at δ 1.5 (3H, OCH₂CH₃) splitted into a triplet because of the two adjacent hydrogen atoms. Similarly, signals at δ 4.30 (2H, OCH₂CH₂) splitted into a quartet. A sharp singlet at δ 2.5 (3H, CH₃) is observed. Signals at δ 7.30–7.65 slightly upfield (3H, benzothiazolyl ring) spread into two groups due to the inductive effect of -OCH₂CH₃ group. One signal at δ 3.25 (2H, NH₂), one sharp signal at δ 2.8 (1H, NH) and a group of signals at δ 7.5–8.0 (5H, C₆H₅NH) were also observed.

Similarly, other azo compounds, viz. 4-benzothiazolylazo-N-thiocarbamoyl-3,5-dimethylpyrazole, 4-benzothiazolylazo-N-thiocarbamoyl-3-methyl-5-amino-(2-chlorophenyl)pyrazole were prepared by taking suitable hydrazones. Their characteristics are given in Table 1.

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References

1. R. G. CHILD, R. G. WILKINSON and A. TOMCU-FUCIK, U.S. Pat. 4,006,234/1977 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1977, 87, 6031)
2. I. M. ROUSHDI, E. S. A. IBRAHIM and H. S. HABIB, *Pharmazie*, 1956, 31, 856.
3. K. N. GAIND and J. M. KHANNA, *Indian J. Pharm.*, 1964, 26, 34.
4. K. N. GAIND and S. K. GULATI, *Indian J. Pharm.*, 1966, 28, 272.
5. L. S. GOODMAN and A. GILMAN, "The Pharmacological Basis of Therapeutics", 4th. ed, MacMillan, New York, 1970, p. 1111.
6. J. L. EVERETT and W. C. J. ROSS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 1972
7. E. C. HERRMANN and J. GRABLICKS, *Cancer Chemother. Rep.*, 1961, 14, 85.
8. E. L. ANDERSON, J. E. CASEY, L. C. GREENE, J. J. JAFFERTY and H. E. REIFF, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1964, 1, 259.
9. R. HIRSCHMANN, N. G. STEINLEERG, E. F. SCHOENEWALDT, W. J. PALWEDA and M. TISCHLER, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1960, 1, 352.

10. J. B. WRIGHT, W. E. DULIN and J. H. MARKILLIE, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1964, 7, 102.
11. R. E. ORTH, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1968, 57, 537.
12. W. WILSON and N. BOTHGLIERI, *Cancer Chemother.*, 1962, 21, 137.
13. C. W. NOELL and C. C. CHENG, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1969, 12, 545.
14. S. RICH and J. G. HORSFAU, *Phytopathology*, 1952, 42, 457.
15. R. JAIN and A. DIXIT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, communicated.

Search for Precocenes in *Ageratum conyzoides* Linn. of North-East India

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PRECOCENE I (2) and **Precocene II (3)** are the first plant anti-juvenile hormones isolated from *Ageratum* (Fam.: Compositae) species that could introduce precocene metamorphosis in insects and are, therefore, potential insecticides¹⁻³. A small annual shrub *A. conyzoides* Linn. and *A. houstonium*⁴ are reported to be good sources for both 2 and 3. It is also reported that while *A. conyzoides* of upper French contains largely a phenolic ester⁵ and that of south India is a source of 2 and a dimer of 3 Bohlman *et al.*⁶ also isolated both 2 and 3 from other Compositae plants. The medicinal importances of *A. conyzoides* such as antitithic⁷, antidysentric⁸ and antibacterial⁹ are reported by several workers. The mode of anti-JH activity¹⁰ and the biosynthesis¹¹ of precocenes are of active interest of several groups.

The potential anti-JH activity of 2 and 3 and lack of data on the presence of these two compounds in different parts of the plant prompted us to undertake this study.

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